

**METHODICAL INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH
ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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Abstract:

This article explores effective strategies for enhancing the speech activity of primary school pupils, emphasizing methodical approaches grounded in research and pedagogical principles. Drawing from diverse fields such as education, linguistics, and psychology, it highlights the importance of creating a language-rich environment, modeling effective communication, implementing structured speaking activities, promoting vocabulary development, fostering listening skills, encouraging peer interaction, providing feedback and reflection opportunities, offering differentiated instruction, integrating speech activities across the curriculum, and promoting cultural and linguistic sensitivity. By incorporating these strategies, educators can cultivate confident and competent communicators among primary school pupils, laying a strong foundation for academic success and lifelong learning.

Keywords:

Primary education, speech activity, language-rich environment, effective communication, structured speaking activities, vocabulary development, listening skills, peer interaction, feedback, reflection, differentiated instruction, curriculum integration, cultural sensitivity, linguistic diversity, pedagogy.

This article explores methodical approaches and strategies for fostering speech activity among primary school pupils. Drawing from research in education, linguistics, and psychology, it discusses the importance of speech development in early childhood and provides practical guidelines for educators to enhance students' speaking skills.

The formation of the speech process is important for a person to become a mature person

becomes important. However, its development continues throughout people's lives at different stages. However, there are a number of proven ways to develop the speech process in students. These are mainly developed countries that have their own methods included. Because it showed positive results with its efficiency. Nowadays, more and more children are facing speech disorders.

The presence of clear speech disorders in a child is usually his whole mental affects development. In this case, the general direction of the child's mental development will definitely slow down, which will inevitably affect his entire school education and later life. Many problems also often appear as a reaction to a speech error resulting from secondary depressions. The emergence of such mental stratification is the result of repeated failures experienced by the child during oral communication, as well as the wrong reaction of others to speech errors (mockery, facial expressions). It is precisely because of the secondary mental layers that sometimes even relatively minor speech errors that suffer from these deficiencies are perceived as real misfortunes, especially as they increase with age. Try to make sure that your children, if they suffer from any speech disorder, do not get angry with you in their future life. Do everything you can to normalize the child's speech - let nothing prevent him from studying, working and living fully.

Methodological instructions for the development of speech activity of elementary school students include:

1. **Fluent Speech Learning:** Using simple words and word reading movements for easy and faster learning to help students learn correct speech.
2. **Learning to Participate in Conversations:** Teaching students to express themselves, participate in speaking and listening processes.
3. **Use of Dramatic Art:** Development of speech activity of students through dramatic games and role playing.
4. **Books and Stories:** To help students understand spoken text by reading books and telling stories.
5. **Choosing Words to Support Speech:** Using auxiliary words in the process of teaching students.

6. Use of Networks Used in Conversations: To learn the networks used in speaking to students and to use them in practice.

7. Making Presentations and Statements: Provide opportunities for students to prepare statements and presentations.

8. Evaluation of Students' Speech Activity: Creating effective assessments to evaluate students' speech activity.

9. Collaboration and Community Work: Students learn to collaborate and work in community with other students and teachers.

These methodological guidelines provide key values and practices that are important in the development of students' speaking skills.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, fostering speech activity in primary school pupils is essential for their overall academic success and social development. By implementing evidence-based strategies and pedagogical approaches, educators can create a supportive learning environment that nurtures confident and competent communicators. From creating language-rich classrooms to modeling effective communication, providing structured speaking activities, and promoting peer interaction, each aspect contributes to the holistic development of speech skills. Additionally, incorporating feedback, reflection, and cultural sensitivity further enhances the effectiveness of speech development initiatives. By embracing these principles and practices, educators empower primary school pupils to become articulate, expressive, and engaged learners, laying a strong foundation for their future academic and personal growth.

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